

Comparative Study of Gellan Gum Derived from Domestic Raw Materials of Kazakhstan and Commercial Gellan

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Abstract. Gellan gum prepared from the domestic raw materials of Kazakhstan was studied by methods of ¹H NMR spectroscopy, FTIR, GPC, TGA and compared with characteristics of commercial gellan gum. Fermentation on glucose-fructose syrup of Zharkent and Burunday corn starch plants (Kazakhstan) by *Sphingomonas paucimobilis* ATCC 31461™ produced a biomass containing a high acyl gellan gum (HAG). The average molecular weights, M_w , M_n , M_z and polydispersity index (PDI) of HAG were determined by GPC. Low acyl gellan (LAG) was obtained by treatment of HAG with alkaline solution. It was shown that the spectral and thermal characteristics of HAG and LAG produced from the glucose-fructose syrup and commercial gellan gum are similar.

1. Introduction

Gellan gum is extracellular polysaccharide industrially produced by bacterium *Sphingomonas paucimobilis*.^[1,2] It is widely applied as gelling, thickening and stabilizing agent in food industry, biotechnology, medicine, pharmacy, and oil recovery.^[3-6] Gellan is composed of glucose (60%), glucuronic acid (20%) and rhamnose (20%) linked in a linear tetrasaccharide repeating unit.^[1,2] There are two types of gellan gum differentiated on the basis of degree of deacetylation: high acyl (HAG) and low acyl (LAG) gellan gum (**Figure S1**)^[7] The

conformational (coil-helix) and phase (sol-gel) behavior of gellan depends on polymer concentration, pH, temperature and the presence of monovalent or divalent cations.^[8] In this regard gellan belongs to stimuli-responsive polymer. A new strategy of gellan production was developed^[9] searching the low-cost sources and media^[10], as well as optimizing the fermentative reaction condition.^[7,11] The use of low-cost substrates such as glucose-fructose syrup of Zharkent and Burunday corn starch plants (Almaty region, Kazakhstan) can help to boost their market competitiveness. In this communication, the process of gellan production from domestic raw materials of Kazakhstan using *S. paucimobilis* ATCC 31461TM is described.

2. Experimental Part

2.1. Materials

Glucose-fructose syrups are commercial products of Zharkent and Burunday corn starch plants (Almaty region, Republic of Kazakshtan). *Sphingomonas paucimobilis* ATCC 31461TM was used in this study. Commercial high acyl (HAG) and low acyl gellan (LAG) were purchased from “Xinjiang Fufeng Biotechnologies Co., Ltd.”, China. Isopropanol ($\geq 99.5\%$, Fischer-Chemicals Oy) was used for precipitation of HAG and LAG. Deuterated water (D₂O, 99% D, Euriso-Top) was used for precipitation of HAG and LAG. Deuterated water (D₂O, 99% D, Euriso-Top) was used in NMR experiments. “BC” medium contained glucose (2%), yeast extract (0.3%), peptone (0.5%), pH = 7.0^[12] and “CP1” medium contained glucose (10%), peptone (0.2%), K₂HPO₄ (0.2%), NaCl (0.2%), MgSO₄ (0.04%), FeSO₄ (0.001%).

2.2. Methods

FTIR spectra were obtained with the help of a Cary 660 ATR-FTIR instrument (Agilent, USA). ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker Avance III 500 spectrometer. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was carried out using a LabSys Evo (Setaram, France) under a nitrogen atmosphere in a temperature range of 25 to 500°C, with a heating rate of 10°C min⁻¹. The dynamic viscosity of the biomass was measured with a Brookfield rotational

viscometer (Brookfield AMETEK DV2TLV, USA). Gel permeable chromatography (GPC) was carried out on a Viscotek GPC/SEC (UK).

2.3. Fermentation of glucose-fructose syrup

The production of gellan gum by *Sphingomonas paucimobilis* from ATCC 31461 was performed on a 50 L stirred bioreactor (ΦC-50, Russia) with 30 L working volume.

3. Results and Discussion

Fermentation on glucose-fructose syrup by *S. paucimobilis* in the media of “BC” and “CP1” produces the biomasses containing HAG (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1. Biomasses obtained upon fermentation of glucose-fructose syrup by *S. paucimobilis* in the media of “BC” (No. 1-4) and “CP1” (No. 5-7)

After thermal treatment of biomass at 90-95 °C during 10-15 min according to Kang et al.^[13] the samples showed the following dynamic viscosities: 22 000 mPa·s (No.1), 18 800 mPa·s (No.2), 3 600 mPa·s (No.5), and 3 900 mPa·s (No.6). Further the samples No. 3,4,6,7 were deacetylated by addition of 1.0 M NaOH at 80 °C for 10 min and the pH was adjusted to 7.0 using 1.0 M HCl. Cell mass from the broth was separated by centrifugation at 8000 rpm for 30 min at 4 °C. The ice-cold three volumes of isopropyl alcohol were then added into supernatant to precipitate the deacetylated gellan. The precipitated LAG was dried to constant mass in hot air oven at 80 °C for 12 h. FTIR spectra of commercial HAG purchased from “Xinjiang Fufeng Biotechnologies Co., Ltd.”, China, and Kazakhstan HAG separated from the fermentation broth are compared in **Figure 3**. In all cases the appearance of intensive bands at 1724-1727 cm⁻¹ is specific for acyl groups of HAG.

Figure 3. FTIR spectra of self-purified (1), technical (2) HAG produced by Xinjiang Fufeng Biotechnologies Co., Ltd. and Kazakhstan HAG (3) obtained by fermentation of glucose-fructose syrup.

Figure 4. FTIR spectra of commercial LAG purchased from Xinjiang Fufeng Biotechnologies Co., Ltd. and Kazakhstan LAG obtained by deacylation of Kazakhstan HAG.

In deacylated gellan gum, or LAG, the intensive peaks at $1724\text{--}1726\text{ cm}^{-1}$ disappear that confirms the elimination of acyl groups from HAG (**Figure 4**). The commercial and Kazakhstan LAG contains the bands at $3340, 1406, 2921, 1622$ and 1037 cm^{-1} that belong to stretching and bending OH, stretching CH, C=O and C-O-C bonds respectively. ^1H NMR spectra of LAG coincide well with literature data^[14] and show the characteristic peaks of CH of rhamnose (5.27 ppm), CH of glucuronic acid (5.09 ppm), and CH_3 of rhamnose (1.86 ppm) (**Figures 5, 6**). ^{13}C NMR spectra of commercial LAG and Kazakhstan LAG are shown in **Figure S2**.

Figure 5. ^1H NMR spectrum of commercial LAG in D_2O at $60\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. $C = 10\text{ mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$

Figure 6. ^1H NMR spectrum of Kazakhstan LAG in D_2O at $60\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. $C = 10\text{ mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$

The weight average (M_w), number average (M_n), and M_z molecular weights and polydispersity index (PDI) of Kazakhstan HAG are presented in **Table 1**. The value of PDI close to 1 indicates on narrow distribution of molecular mass of HAG.

Table 1. Average molecular weights and PDI of Kazakhstan HAG

Polymer	Molecular weights, Dalton			PDI (M_w/M_n)
	M_w	M_n	M_z	
HAG	343 500	333 000	360 000	1.03

Thermogravimetric curves of commercial HAG and Kazakhstan HAG was compared (**Figure S3**). The decomposition temperature of both samples lies in the region of $250\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and completely coincides. Aqueous solutions 0.25 and 0.5% Kazakhstan LAG showed an excellent gelation property upon addition of salts (NaCl and CaCl_2) in the range of concentration 0.01-1.0M (**Figure S4**).

4. Conclusion

By fermentation on glucose-fructose syrup of Zharkent and Burunday corn starch plants by *S. paucimobilis* the high and low acyl gellan gums were produced. They were characterized by various physico-chemical methods and compared with commercial gellan produced in China.

In perspective the developed technology of gellan production from the domestic raw materials of Kazakhstan may be scaled up and used in food industry and oil recovery.

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High- and low acyl gellan samples were produced from the glucose-fructose syrup of Zharkent and Burunday corn starch plants (Almaty region, Kazakhstan) by fermentation with strain *Sphingomonas paucimobilis*. Their structure and physico-chemical characteristics established by NMR, FTIR, GPC, TGA and elemental analysis coincide well with commercial gellan that is produced by “Xinjiang Fufeng Biotechnologies Co., Ltd.”, China.

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Supporting Information

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Figure S1. Repeating monomeric units of high acyl (HAG) and low acyl (LAG) gellan gum.

Figure S2. ¹³C NMR spectra of commercial (a) and Kazakhstan (b) LAG at 60 °C.

Figure S3. TGA curves of commercial (1) and Kazakhstan (2) HAG.

Figure S4. Gelation of Kazakhstan LAG in the presence of NaCl (1) and CaCl₂ (2).